

Matriks GAUSS

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Definisi

Matriks Gauss:

$G_i = I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T$, dengan $\underline{m} = [0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0 \ m_{i+1} \ m_{i+2} \ \dots]^T$,
elemen vektor $m_k = 0$ untuk $k \leq i$.

Jika $i = 1$, maka diperoleh matriks Gauss 3x3:

$$\begin{aligned} G_1 = I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_1^T &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_2 & 0 & 0 \\ m_3 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ m_2 & 1 & 0 \\ m_3 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Definisi (selesai)

$$G_i A = \left(I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) A = A + \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T A ; \text{ distributiv!}$$

Nilai m_k dalam vektor m dipilih sedemikian sehingga Baris- k dan kolom- i matriks $G_i A$ samadengan nol.

Contoh

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad G_1 A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$
$$G_1 A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_2 & 2m_2 & 3m_2 \\ m_3 & 2m_3 & 3m_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Berapa nilai m_2 dan m_3 agar kolom-1 baris- k (>1) matriks $G_1 A$ samadengan $\underline{0}$?

Jawab: $m_2 = -4$ dan $m_3 = -7$.

$$\underline{m} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -4 & -7 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

Contoh (lanjutan)

$$G_1 A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -4 & -8 & -12 \\ -7 & -14 & -21 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & -6 & -21 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_2(G_1 A) &= (I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_2^T)(G_1 A) = (G_1 A) + \underline{m} \underline{e}_2^T (G_1 A) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & -6 & -21 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ m_3 \end{bmatrix} [0 \ 1 \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & -6 & -21 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & -6 & -21 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -3m_3 & -6m_3 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

karena dipilih $m_3 = -2$, maka

Contoh (selesai)

$$G_2(G_1A) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & -6 & -21 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 6 & 12 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix}$$

adalah MSA (=matriks segitiga atas)

Invers matriks Gauss, G_i^{-1}

$$G_i^{-1} = I - \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T$$

berbeda dengan G_i hanya pada operator penjumlahan.

Bukti:
$$\begin{aligned} G_i^{-1} G_i &= \left(I - \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \left(I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \\ &= I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T - \underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T - \left(\underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \left(\underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \\ &= I \end{aligned}$$

kolom-i bertemu
dengan baris-i (=0), dan saat
kolom-(i+1) bertemu
baris-(i+1) ($\neq 0$), kolom-(i+1)
malah bernilai 0,
sehingga perkalian dimaksud
menghasilkan matriks nol.

$$\left(\underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \left(\underline{m} \underline{e}_i^T \right) \rightarrow$$

			i			
	0	...	0	0	...	0
	⋮					⋮
	0	...	0	0	...	0
i+1	0	...	0	m_{i+1}	...	0
	⋮			⋮		⋮
	0	...	0	m_n	...	0

Menuju faktorisasi

Hasil contoh sebelumnya:

$$G_1 = I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_1^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -4 \\ -7 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -4 & 1 & 0 \\ -7 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G_2 = I + \underline{m} \underline{e}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G_2(G_1 A) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix}$$

Dapat dicari G_1^{-1} dan G_2^{-1} , yaitu:

Menuju faktorisasi (lanjutan)

$$G_1^{-1} = I - \underline{m} \underline{e}_1^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -4 \\ -7 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G_2^{-1} = I - \underline{m} \underline{e}_2^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$G_1^{-1} G_2^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

adalah **MSB** (matriks segitiga bawah) satuan.

Menuju faktorisasi (selesai)

$$(G_1^{-1}G_2^{-1})(G_2G_1A) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

mendapatkan matriks **A** kembali.

Diperoleh faktorisasi matriks A sebagai berikut:

$$A = (G_1^{-1}G_2^{-1})(G_2G_1A)$$

$$A = LU, \text{ dengan}$$

$$L = G_1^{-1}G_2^{-1} \text{ adalah MSB - satuan dan}$$

$$U = G_2G_1A \text{ adalah MSA.}$$

Solusi $Ax=b$

$$A\underline{x} = \underline{b}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 6 \\ 7 & 8 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$LU\underline{x} = \underline{b}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$L\underline{y} = \underline{b}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

dengan

$$\underline{y} = U\underline{x}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Solusi $Ax=b$ (selesai)

Pemecahan $Ly=b$:

$$y_1 = 2$$

$$4y_1 + y_2 = 1 \Leftrightarrow y_2 = 1 - 4(2) = -7$$

$$7y_1 + 2y_2 + y_3 = 3 \Leftrightarrow y_3 = 3 - 7(2) - 2(-7) = 3$$

$$\text{diperoleh: } \underline{y} = [y_1 \quad y_2 \quad y_3]^T = [2 \quad -7 \quad 3]^T$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 0 \\ 7 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

Pemecahan $Ux=y$:

$$-9x_3 = 3 \Leftrightarrow x_3 = -\frac{1}{3}$$

$$-3x_2 + (-6)x_3 = -7 \Leftrightarrow x_2 = (-7 - (-6)(-\frac{1}{3})) / (-3) = 3$$

$$x_1 + 2x_2 + 3x_3 = 2 \Leftrightarrow x_1 = 2 - 2(3) - 3(-\frac{1}{3}) = -3$$

$$\text{diperoleh: } \underline{x} = [x_1 \quad x_2 \quad x_3]^T = [-3 \quad 3 \quad -\frac{1}{3}]^T$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & -3 & -6 \\ 0 & 0 & -9 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ -7 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$